

Expect the Unexpected: The Impact of Inflation and the Importance of Malaysian Youths Having a Financial Plan

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Introduction

In Malaysia, Millennials and the Generation Z hang out with friends at least once or twice a month, and one of their most preferred places to do so is at a Mamak restaurant. They usually have *teh tarik* before getting something to eat. This all-time favourite drink for Malaysians readily available in Mamak restaurants, stalls, roadside stalls, and kopitiam has seen a price increase.

The price of a cup in 1957, the year we gained independence, was 5 cents. , with a 40 to 60 per cent increase in price (CompareHero, 2022). However, according to a 2022 study of the Department of Statistics Malaysia (DOSM), the average price for a cup of *teh tarik* was RM1.64 in 2021, a slight increase from RM1.59 in 2019 and RM1.61 in 2020 (DOSM, 2022a). Similar findings by the Social Wellbeing Research Centre (SWRC) in 2022 also highlighted that the average price for a cup of *teh tarik* is RM1.60 within the Klang Valley area. But the recent spike in food ingredients due to inflation worldwide has caused restaurants to raise the price of *teh tarik* from RM2.00 to RM2.50 to ensure their survival and absorb the rising cost (theVibes.com, 2022; RinggitPlus, 2022).

In addition, the prices of other Malaysian "must-haves" for breakfast like *roti canai*, *nasi lemak*, *kopi-O* and *teh-O* have also risen. Eating out has become more expensive, an issue often talked about.

Inflation Rate Among ASEAN Countries

Inflation is when the prices of goods and services increase, which will reduce the consumer's purchasing power in the long term (Investopedia, 2022). Figure 1 shows the inflation rate in ASEAN, and we can see that Malaysia is in fifth position. Brunei and Indonesia have a lower inflation rate. As we are entering the recovery phase after a 2-year lockdown due to the COVID-19 pandemic, it is understandable that our economy has not recovered sufficiently yet.

Inflation also causes other ripple effects like increases in prices of goods and services (i.e., housing, food commodities, transportation, healthcare, and taxes). In Malaysia, the rise in the price of necessities will impact the middle-income group (B40) living in the big cities and employment hubs like Kuala Lumpur, Putrajaya, Shah Alam and Johor Bharu. Figures for the inflation rate by state in 2021 show that the state of Selangor and the Federal Territory of Putrajaya have the highest inflation rate at 2.7 per cent out of all 13 states (DOSM, 2022a). Those who are hardest hit are youths who have just joined the workforce.

Monthly Expenses

Table 1 shows the estimated monthly expenses for single persons (public transport users and car owners) in all cities in Malaysia, using Belanjawanku 2022 as a benchmark for affordable living expenses for Malaysian youths. The estimated monthly income for public transport users is RM1900 and RM2570 (this is as the Klang Valley is the most densely populated area in Malaysia, where most people from other states migrate to find better job opportunities). The suggested value comprises multiple baskets such as food, housing, transportation, utility, personal care, healthcare, ad-hoc expenses, social participation, and discretionary expenses. A fresh graduate should land a job that offers a monthly salary starting or within the range of RM2500 (for public transport users) and RM3000 (for car owners), where the excess is for contingencies. The suggested estimated monthly expenses of RM1900 (public transport user) and RM2570 (car owner) are just a number for the fresh graduate to have a decent and acceptable standard of living. This finding also aligns with iPrice Group Sdn Bhd that stated that the estimated living cost for a single person in Kuala Lumpur is RM3,300 a month (The Malaysia Reserve, 2021). On the other hand, a study by Bank Negara Malaysia recorded a slightly lower amount of RM2,700 for a single person's estimated monthly expenses in Kuala Lumpur (Chong & Khong, 2018).

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Table 1: Belanjawanku 2021: Estimated Monthly Expenses for Single (Public Transport User) and Single (Car Owner) for All Cities in Malaysia

City/Region	Single (Public Transport User)	Single (Car Owner)	Increment from Single Public Transport to Single Car Owner (in %)
Klang Valley*	1900	2570	135
Alor Setar	1500	2030	135
Kota Kinabalu	1670	2190	131
Johor Bahru	1740	2270	130
Kuala Terengganu	1600	2130	133
Kuching	1640	2170	132
Kuantan	1670	2190	131
Kota Bahru	1500	2070	138
Georgetown	1790	2390	133
Ipoh (prelim)	1630	2220	136
Seremban (prelim)	1680	2260	134
Melaka (prelim)	1690	2230	131

Source: Social Wellbeing Research Centre, SWRC, (2022)

Housing

Most youths will at one point need to have their own house. Due to inflation, their dream of having their own home will not materialize soon as the housing price in Malaysia keeps increasing yearly. Figure 2 displays that the trend of housing prices in Malaysia, which marks a rise from 2012 until last year, with a slight decrease in 2018 and 2019 but staying constant until 2021 (Q2). Overall, we can conclude that the median house price in Malaysia is not astronomically higher compared to other Asian countries like Hong Kong, China and Singapore. The situation has worsened with the price of construction materials rising this year, adversely affecting the housing price. A survey conducted by Real Estate and Housing Developers Association Malaysia (REHDA) reveals that the housing prices are anticipated to increase by an average of 19 per cent this year. Among the construction materials that show a price increase are concrete (16 per cent), sand (18 per cent), cement (19 per cent), steel (38 per cent), timber (52 per cent) and aluminium (55 per cent) (The Edge Market, 2022). This situation has diminished the purchasing power of youths, which is already limited by lower wages and rising cost of living.

Figure 2: Residential Prices Quarterly/Yearly Update Malaysia: Median House Price Trend From 2010 Until Q2 2021

Source: National Property Information Centre, NAPIC, (2021b)

Statistics for housing prices by the state clearly show that housing prices in Kuala Lumpur, Putrajaya, Penang, and Selangor are relatively higher than in other states, with an average price of RM445,075. The capital of Malaysia, Kuala

Lumpur, has the highest housing prices in Malaysia at RM480,000. To attain a housing loan for this kind of house price, youths need to land a job that offers at least RM4,000 a month as their starting salary. As for Perlis, Kedah and Melaka, the housing price in these cities is relatively lower, with an average of RM211,66 (NAPIC, 2021a).

Based on the report for total Malaysian income in 2020, the mean and median monthly salaries in Malaysia are RM2,933 and RM2,062 respectively (DOSM, 2022b). The minimum amount required to have a decent life is still unattainable. Getting a housing loan is considered a luxury due to the lower median wage in Malaysia. With a starting salary ranging from RM2,000 to RM2,500 for fresh graduates, the affordability of buying a house is an issue for low- and medium-income groups in Malaysia. Housing prices are constantly increasing, but salaries are not catching up with the price increase. Yearly salary increments are also relatively small. There is sometimes no annual salary increment even after five years of working in the same organization.

Inflation by Main Group

A small and, on some occasions, no yearly salary increment, higher living costs, increasing housing prices, and higher inflation have further exacerbated the problem for youths living in big cities. Figure 2 shows that inflation has caused the prices of several main group items such as transport, food and beverages, household equipment and routine household maintenance and housing, water, electricity, gas and other fuels to have increased drastically. All of the stated items are essential and considered daily-use commodities. The annual inflation rate for these four primary groups is 15.8 per cent per month, while the highest inflation rate among the leading group is transportation at 11 per cent. This means that another 11 per cent in expenses is added to the amount spent by youths to commute to work and back. One of the options for the youth that live in big cities like Kuala Lumpur, Putrajaya, Shah Alam and Johor Bharu is to use public transportation, for example, LRT, MRT, Monorail in Kuala Lumpur; transit and Rapid K.L. Bus in Putrajaya; free bus in Shah Alam; and Bas Muafakat in Johor. Another viable option is using a motorcycle as the primary vehicle for commuting to work. Using motorcycles or scooters is more practical and can aid youths to save money on petrol, parking and maintenance.

Source: Department of Statistics Malaysia, DOSM, (2022a)

Inflation for Subgroup of Food & Beverage

Figure 3 shows the impact of inflation on the subgroup of food and beverages like oils and fats, meat, fish and seafood, milk, cheese and eggs, and homecooked food. It is quite alarming as the total inflation rate for the five most consumed food and beverages items is 14 per cent.

Source: Department of Statistics Malaysia, DOSM, (2022a)

Even having food cooked at home has a 2.1 inflation rate, meaning there is no difference anymore between cooking at home for lunch and dinner for a single person compared with having lunch and dinner at a Mamak restaurant. With the ongoing war between Russia and Ukraine, the food supply chain has already been disrupted and caused some commodity prices to soar. Currently, the cost of chicken, one of the staple foods in Malaysia aside from rice, is higher than the ceiling price of RM8.90 per kilogramme. The same trend also is projected in the next month when the price is floated due to the end of the maximum retail price scheme on June 30 (New Straits

Times, 2022). That would mean that Malaysians need to endure the rising prices of daily food and beverages like meat, fish, milk, cheese and chicken for some time until the situation improves. Even with drastic action, like halting chicken imports to Singapore has not been enough to stabilize the price of chicken in Malaysia.

Conclusion and Key Takeaways

In conclusion, firstly, youths need to prepare themselves for unprecedented events in the future. Financial planning is crucial in the early stages of life as they will have the intention to get married and subsequently have their own family. Early preparation will enable them to have some backup and prepare for the worst. Further, youths should take a loan commitment based on their capacity. Having to take a loan is inevitable, but take it for necessary things such as education, car, housing, investment, credit cards, etc. It is not a good financial decision to take a loan beyond their capability to repay, as it can lead to early bankruptcy. In addition, the government announcement to stop providing subsidies to chicken breeders means the price of this food item will increase in the future and directly impact the monthly expenses of youths. Youths need to revise their monthly budget and spend more prudently during this challenging time.

